

Mentoring a New Researcher: A Teacher's Learning

Pralhad Adhikari*

Abstract

Mentorship is the formal or informal relationship that empowers the less experienced professional with guidance from the more experienced professional. Mentorship can be used as a part of andragogy. This autoethnography presents my lessons about academic research mentoring, as a university teacher who supervised multiple theses in a master's degree. I share some experiences of how I evolved as a research supervisor in more than 5 years and insights for more effective supervision of a new researcher.

Keywords: andragogy, early career researcher, master's degree, research supervision, thesis.

Introduction

Mentoring or coaching (Burley & Pomphrey, 2011) or supervising (Lunsford et al., 2017) is the professional relationship between a more experienced person and a less experienced person that sets the goals to empower the latter in a fixed time period. It involves providing mentees with various types of support, such as advising, coaching, and role modeling (Gruber et al., 2020). This relationship serves the functions of career enhancement and improvement of psychosocial skills (Carol A. Mullen & Klimaitis, 2021). Mentees value certain behaviors in mentors, including integrity, guidance, and constructive feedback. There are differences between formal and informal mentoring, with informal mentoring being associated with a greater range of mentoring functions and higher satisfaction. Effective mentoring can enhance the scholarly productivity of proteges and prevent their attrition from the academic degree or even profession (Gruber et al., 2020). Similarly, mentoring the graduate students is helpful to empower them with skills such as time management, and network-building. Mentoring can be used to socialize somebody new in the industry (Thomas et al., 2015). It may be helpful for those who come from a marginalized background. Mentoring can be used to improve academic performance, retain students in higher education and ease their transition to higher levels in the undergraduate level (Lunsford et al., 2017). For graduate students, socialization and scholarly productivity can be the potential benefits (Lunsford et al., 2017) among others. Mentoring may occur informally, for example, a study (Searby et al., 2015) found that female administrators in universities find mentors informally who help them as sponsors, teachers, counselors, and spiritual guides. Mentorship may be helpful to mentors' growth also (Lucey & White, 2017).

Mentorship has the potential to be used as a teaching method or andragogy. Adhikari (2022b) has suggested mentoring for the Nepalese psychological community for growth, satisfaction, and productivity. This suggestion can carry over to other educational settings. Eastern cultures like Nepal

* Assistant Professor (Psychology), Department of Psychology and Philosophy, Tri-Chandra Multiple College, Kathmandu, pralhad.adhikari@gmail.com

and China have a long tradition of mentorship (Adhikari, 2022b; Lee & Bush, 2003). A faculty can assume several roles like that of advisor, instructor, employer, and agent of socialization (Lechuga, 2011) for their protege. Lee and Bush have recommended including mentorship as a formal part of the curriculum. The ways to plan, establish, operate, and evaluate mentoring relationships need to be explored.

Statement of Problem

Mentoring is a buzzword. Still, how can one be an effective mentor has not been discussed much from a supervisor’s perspective. A mentor’s involvement needs to be shared to gain insights about how other mentors can act more effectively. Especially, in the domain of research mentorship, the mentors’ narrative needs to be shared more if pedagogy at the college and university levels is to be enhanced.

Objectives

An objective is to share the experiences of mentoring. Another objective is to interpret them in the broader practice of research mentoring and its effectiveness. My narrative as a supervisor of 18 MA (Psychology)’s thesis researchers has been shared.

Method

The autoethnography method has been adopted. It is related to explaining socio-cultural actions in relation to a researcher’s personal experience. It lets us present our stories through cultural lenses (Adams et al., 2015). We can use our experiences to critically evaluate culture (including andragogy). We use reflexivity to interrogate self-society overlap. The experiences have been recollected with help of files stored on my computer. I also used the list of my proteges stored in the internet to bring up their imagery and remember critical incidents in our relationships. I used thematic analysis to process these experiences.

Results

I divide this section into several categories under three themes as shown in the table below:

Table 1 Factors that determine the effectiveness of mentoring relationship

Mentor-related	Protégé-related	University-related
Socialization of protégé	Management skills	Networking (A poor networker)
Empathy (protégé perspective)	English language barrier	Connect to funders (pain of a penniless researcher)
Evolution (learning attitude)	Willing but unable	
Delegation	Statistics: a puzzle	
Decrease online feedback	Planning life and something else	
Provide resources (pandemic experience)		
Things to improve		

Socialization

The new researchers may be clueless about the relationship with the supervisor. So, I have the practice of socializing students via a written document named “Conditions for Thesis Supervision”. It is not a legal document, but still, it serves as a standard to discipline both the mentor and protégé. Even though it has a strict-sounding nomenclature, this document is a socialization tool that discusses the limits and boundaries of limitations. For example, to maintain a work-life balance, I let students call me on workdays only and between office hours. This clearly communicates to the protégé that they should honor the personal life of a supervisor. Similarly, the socialization document clarifies to students that they can communicate openly, they can defend their position with evidence, they should try to arrange a meeting weekly, and they should ask permission from test-makers if they are to use any standardized psychological tests. Below are some suggestions I offer to students regarding communication.

- “I prefer face-to-face communication. Make the habit of meeting me weekly with updates about your work and progress. If you want to meet me, call me the preceding day and we will fix the time.
- You may use email if you are okay with a late response. Please do not send files by email for feedback. Bring the printout of things you have written during a meeting.
- I do not entertain even a single inquiry about administrative aspects related to the thesis. Contact the MA coordinator or related employees at the Department/College for such inquiries”.

The Protege Perspective

An Australian professor mentored me for a study that checked if sources of social support acted as moderators in the relationship between functional impairment and depression (Adhikari & McLaren, 2023). In the course of mentorship, I sometimes had reservations to contact my mentor even though she was open to any type of questions and support. She had eliminated hierarchy; she had allowed me to address her by name but I felt (or self-perceived) a power differential. She was professionally demanding, yet very kind to allow her mentee enough time to do the needed. After we were done with proposal, we had to adapt it to Nepal Health Research Council (NHRC)’s criteria and this adaptation took weeks. When a journal rejected our article and I had to adapt our article for another journal, I was very embarrassed because new adaptation took months for me. At moments, I felt like quitting. Nevertheless, I had made myself ready to relax and persevere, as a result of growth. Moreover, my mentor’s support also played significant role. She mailed me sometimes and I would rekindle or get triggered to do the next thing after a long stagnation. She corrected the errors with enough feedback, and I never felt irritation in her tone despite my silly lapses. As a mentee, I felt that being unable to catch up with the mentor’s expectations is a big barrier to an effective mentoring relationship and consequently the effectiveness of the relationship. Even though our research got published finally, we could have been quicker if I communicated

my problems more frankly with her. I underutilized my opportunity. I see the same problem with my proteges. I expect their queries and always cooperate to openly communicate with their queries, but they get contactless for months and do away with their work in haste at the last hour. They hesitate to communicate even in the moments when they are clueless about how to move forward.

An Evolving Supervisor

Supervisors also grow as they supervise several proteges. They evolve as a researcher themselves. They also change the way they supervise. Based on their experiences with a protégé, they alter the way they maintain the relationship with a new protégé. I have the habit of documenting my learning as a supervisor. Since many students are in the hurry to do away with their degree completion, they have a tendency to copy the contents from the internet or submit the work they submitted earlier for another degree. As a part of quality control, I now let students know and sign the terms and conditions of the supervision relationship in which I clarify the protégé about open communication, accessing the resources I provide to the protégé, and codes of conduct like coming on time for a meeting. Signing, I believe, increases their commitment to genuinely working, openly communicating, and doing the needed to accomplish a research project. Before, I used to provide feedback via email but I realized that feedback is not very effective via mail. Now I have evolved and prefer meeting in person with printout for feedback. Before, I did not have any resources to offer but after the COVID-19-induced lockdown, I began a YouTube channel, and after 2021, I published a reference book that provides ideas to prepare consent forms, conduct the study and analyze data. Similarly, I posted my research and review articles for free via Academia and ResearchGate, the two social media of researchers. My socialization document has the following suggestions for protégé:

- “Watch all relevant videos at <https://www.youtube.com/PralhadAdhikari/videos> carefully.
- Study some works at https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Pralhad_Adhikari/publications or <https://tribhuvan.academia.edu/PralhadAdhikari/> and get ideas for how to complete research.
- Buy a book titled ‘Research Methodology: Psychology / Social Work’ published by Asmita Books Publisher at Putalisadak (in front of Shankardev Campus). It is written for MA students and is compulsory.”

As I have evolved, I have learned several things from experiences. For example, I have learned to formalize and standardize the relationship. My socialization document is an example of the management skill I learned. If I did not document, I would have forgotten some of my lessons, and the mentoring relationship would encounter the same errors repeatedly.

The Increasing Delegation

Adhikari (2022a) has suggested removing hierarchy in a student-teacher relationship because these blocks open communication. The students need to be given more autonomy; they should be

challenged. The mentoring relationship should be based on trust and equality. The mentor provides moral support and expertise to the mentee (Awaya et al., 2003). In my experience, the students need to be motivated to work harder and challenged to solve the problems on their way. However, how to motivate is a puzzle, even though we have multiple theories of motivation at hand.

I do not impose ideas on proteges; they have the ability to decide. I just tell them the options or conventions. They have to decide which one among the options is best. They can defend their position and retain it if my suggestions are not suitable for them. However, with greater power (of decision-making) comes greater responsibility. In the socialization document I have made, the following points highlight my protégé's authority to decide:

- “Please make changes according to comments/feedback. If you want to defend your position, do it with evidence. Communicate fearlessly.
- I do not want perfect results. I want you to try perfectly. Even though I am your supervisor, you should take full responsibility for your thesis. I suggest things but the decision to keep them on or omit from the thesis is entirely yours. So, by the completion of the report, you need to build on confidence to defend your thesis totally on your own.

A solution to the problem of students being clueless about proposal-making or being rejected after submitting the proposal is to establish a convention of making a concept paper by student, assigning the supervisor, and preparing a proposal under the supervision of a mentor. This practice is currently being practiced in the Central Department of Psychology (CDoPsy). However, a different mode of selecting a research problem should not be stopped. For example, the professors can involve their students in some of their research projects like the University Grants Commission (UGC) is encouraging (University Grants Commission, 2021) to do so.

The Decreasing Online Feedback

Some proteges might think that acquiring online feedback would be better than meeting the supervisor in person because such feedback saves their time and travel cost. However, the new researchers benefit more from in-person feedback in my opinion. When they meet the supervisors face-to-face, they can interact more and get the solutions instantly often. Moreover, they learn to value professional relationships. When they bring the printouts, the supervisor can mark the mistakes or weaknesses and they can witness them directly (or get real-time comments). During socialization, I suggest proteges make a diary to write comments and their replies (based on the changes to the thesis they make). In the Master of Counseling Program of Tribhuvan University, there is a practice of documenting and mailing the comments from the external examiner in a specific format. This is a good beginning and can be extended to a mentor-protégé relationship also. There is a problem, however. The teachers (or professors) have to use their private resources to go online and mail the comments, and in my case at least, providing online comments is not possible. I live 36 km away from TriChandra College and carrying computers to the office is cumbersome. The college has not provided personal cabinets,

computers, and internet to its teachers yet. So, without infrastructure, this mode of feedback cannot be made a rule. It is not that I did not provide feedback online ever. In the initial years of assistant professorship, I did, but I realized that most of the students did not attend to the comments carefully. My personal life was also consumed by professional tasks. So, I turned off online feedback mode.

Regarding the feedback, I socialize proteges in the ways mentioned below:

- “I suggest you maintain a comment/thesis diary. Note the comments down as I provide them to you in a meeting. Also, note where and how you addressed them. You should report to me how you addressed them in the next meeting.
- Please make changes according to comments/feedback. If you want to defend your position, do it with evidence. Communicate fearlessly.
- What if you do not address the feedback without proper defense? I may reject to supervise you. Do not take the rejection personally. It will be your carelessness being rejected, not you.
- Bring both the printouts to our meeting: the one in which you got the comment and the one in which you made changes.”

The Pandemic Experience

The COVID-19 pandemic taught us many lessons for life. It was a crisis but people adapted to it despite the lockdown (Adhikari, 2020) after some time passed. Some students were in touch via email communication. It was a time when we had a lot of confusion. The proteges mailed me and I engrossed myself in their documents onscreen. The longer the onscreen time, the higher the mental health consequence was (Neophytou et al., 2019; Twenge & Farley, 2021). Because of the digital file not being completely seen at once and maybe we are not habituated to reading it, the students did not address the comments properly, and the same comment had to be repeatedly given. Some proteges have the tendency to assign their tasks to a supervisor and some even try to place the blame on the supervisor if they are shown lacking by examiners. To reduce this problem of diffusion of responsibility, I socialize them by informing them early to own their work.

- “Professors do not do work for students. So, try your best as advised. Do not expect me to do any work for you. I am here just to guide you ... by the completion of the report, you need to build on confidence to defend your thesis totally on your own.”

A Youtuber

I tried to automate my teaching when I had to tediously repeat the instruction for students to train them in citation and data analysis including statistical calculation. This project available at <https://www.youtube.com/PralhAdhikari/videos> was begun during the first round of the COVID-19 pandemic (or the first lockdown) in 2020. Since then, I have made and posted 70 videos about SPSS, Excel, NVivo, Mendeley, Zotero, and other technologies that I know related to research. The supervisors

now have the facility of using social media or other internet technology to let students repeatedly watch their instruction. Students mainly panic after they encounter with data analysis step. Many students in the Department of Psychology have dropped out after being unable to analyze quantitative data. Using multidimensional instructional methods is helpful to reduce statistics anxiety (Pan & Tang, 2005). So, YouTube is my way of instructing. In the socialization document, I mention:

- “Use Mendeley or Zotero for citation and references management. Their tutorials are available in the Nepali language on my YouTube channel. Do not believe in the software blindly. Use your judgment to decide if the outputs are right.
- Watch all relevant videos at <https://www.youtube.com/PralhadAdhikari/videos> carefully.”

Interestingly, during the pandemic, when meeting proteges was not possible, I sent the feedback to them with video messages uploaded on YouTube privately. When I have to bulk-train students for a bachelor’s degree, I use the ‘Unlisted’ option of video publication on this platform.

The Uncanny Convention: Proposal Without Guidance

There is a convention of letting students present proposals to the college and assigning a supervisor. I find this convention strange. Even though the students study two subjects entirely dedicated to research methods and they should be ready to prepare a proposal on their own, the supervision from the phase of proposal preparation can help both the mentor and protégé have a cognitive map of where they are heading. The student can have an easier and clearer way to blaze the trail they are about to walk. Moreover, many students seem to be clueless about how to begin research at the end of the fourth semester despite their studying Research Methods and doing several research-based assignments (Adhikari, 2022a). I encourage my students to consult with me from the proposal preparation phase. If they happen to submit a proposal with copied content, it gets rejected as mentioned in a point in my socialization document.

- “If your proposal is not strong or healthy (i.e., plagiarized), I will assign you the topic of my choice.
- If you are confused about your topic or not committed to it, you may even discuss a new one.
- If you are clueless about research, you can take my topic and get guidance from scratch to complete your thesis.
- If your thesis is related to (mental) health, I suggest you acquire ethical approval from Nepal Health Research Council (NHRC) and aim for the publication of research in a good international journal. You can submit a proposal online. Go to <https://erb.nhrc.gov.np/>”

Undocumented Feedback

The feedback lost in oblivion can reinvent the wheel, or create discord in the relationship between mentor and mentee. The students may not address the comments because of any reasons; the

mentors have to waste resources by repeatedly suggesting the same thing. As mentioned earlier, a comment diary is a solution to the feedback getting lost unattended. Sometimes, it is interesting to show the comments given and documented earlier.

Outdated (and dominating!) Examiners

The external examiners, generally retired professors, stop getting updated on the latest trends in the industry. Many a time, they base their judgment on their old-day practices. When the proteges get evaluated in that manner, they are intimidated. Sometimes, external examiners are so overpowering and rude, they constantly humiliate students. They forget that the students today can be professors like them tomorrow. Even rejection can be done politely but some external examiners seem not to have learned ways to provide feedback modestly. To adapt to such a situation, I orientate my proteges with the following instructions:

- “After you are done with the thesis, prepare a PowerPoint presentation for thesis defense. Include the major parts of the thesis briefly. Make the slides graphical. Do not miss out Introduction, Methods, Results (table and graphs), and Discussion.
- Be confident to present. It is just speaking out about what you have really done. So, you need not fear. Bring a notebook and note down comments given by examiners. Do not get defensive as they comment. Humbly, you may defend as you get a chance to speak. Please note that Nepali culture promotes yes-men. So, active listening is advised. Smile as you get the comments. Smile as you present your matters.
- After you present/defend your thesis, consult with me about the comments of the examiners. After the final correction, you need to submit the printout to me in a meeting. Only after that, you have to do the hard binding”.

A Poor Networker

Early career researchers benefit from networks. However, I should confess that I am not a proactive networker because I am an introvert. In many colleges in Nepal, thesis presentations are not publicly announced. They should be used as a ceremony for networking opportunities. Like-minded investigators may join; the knowledge can be shared and the door for other studies may open. In the psychology field of Nepal primarily, summits, conferences, seminars, workshops, and presentations are rarely held. They should be increased. The heads and coordinators should pay attention to this issue.

The Pain of Penniless Researchers: Where are the Funders

When psychology graduates work with sensitive and taboo issues, they often encounter underprivileged participants. Even the human participants expect some remuneration. So, the early career researchers including the student researchers have the pain of affording many expenses such as travel costs, communication expenses, and printing costs. In Nepal, in the public domain such

as in daily newspapers, very few funders that support social science (or psychology) research have been noticed. A single event cannot be generalized. An organization named Ageing Nepal had shared a notice for fellowship. I shared the notice with students in the thesis year with the promise to mentor them but no student contacted me. The students also may not be skilled to conduct the study or serious about research as a career. A fact is clear: there are very few funders in Nepal who support social science studies. Tribhuvan University and UGC funds are noteworthy mentions. Recently, some governmental bodies have started to fund the research related to their issues. For example, the Commission for Investigation of Authority had announced scholarships to fund studies related to issues of good governance or corruption (Commission for Investigation of Abuse of Authority, 2022). Other organizations willing to exercise evidence-based practice should step in to fund social science studies.

Management Skills

The research project's completion needs some managerial skills. Managers need technical, conceptual, and human skills (Robbins & Judge, 2022, p. 40). So, a researcher is a kind of manager. For planning the research to building relationships with mentors and participants uses technical, conceptual, and human skills.

A Case of an Introvert

A student, who I had professed during their bachelor's degree, of CDoPsy suffered from an anxiety disorder. Other life problems were to blame too but their introversion came on their way in research completion. They were talented in academic domains, but reluctant to interact with strangers. This impaired their progress and procrastinated on their thesis research. Even though they denied many jobs offers to complete their research, they were impeded by their lack of human skills, and their research project had to suffer.

A solution to such problems in conducting research can be creatively solved. For example, a researcher can hire an assistant for data collection and train them well to accomplish the task. If somebody feels uncomfortable meeting people to collect data in person, they can design an online survey. Research problems should be feasible to study. In other words, a researcher should choose problems that they can handle, methods that they can manage, or a breadth of topic that they can control.

The Protege Reaction

If the main driver for research were passion, the story would have been different. However, students place degree acquisition on top. Skills are more important than degrees or marks. When the students understand this well, their passion may increase. Some students show a willingness to accomplish a lot in the field of research psychology, however, their excitement fades away when they are embroiled in the practical issues of life. I had a few students who were rude to me, a few

others who hurried to pass out without doing the minimum, and who even tried to present the theses presented somewhere else. Many students were humble and willing to do their tasks but their feeble research knowledge hampered them. Few proteges were very proactive, independent, and creative. They had to be only facilitated. Prodigious proteges obviously do away with research sooner; inexperienced students may take longer. To address the behavioral issues, the college/university management should have clear guidelines. The power differential is a protector sometimes but it also is a barrier. Adhikari (2022a) has suggested removing the hierarchy in a mentoring relationship. Lack of clear formatting guidelines, for example, creates ambiguity and the mentoring relationship also has to suffer.

The Language Barrier: Is English a Skill?

Many students are seen to be in difficulty because of their lack of English skills. Since many resources are found in this language, it is a plus if they are already dexterous in it. Theoretically, English is not a skill per se and it can be compensated if you are adept at using technology these days. However, if you lack both English and internet skills, then you may really lag behind other researchers who possess these. In Nepal, minimum English reading and writing proficiency are needed if early career researchers want to get ahead in psychology. Still, I believe that English skills should not be an obstacle. I socialize proteges to seek help from other people if they are less skillful in English.

- “You may need to translate psychological tests to Nepali. Do not use Google Translate. It is not accurate. You may need to contact the creator of the tests for permission to use them in Nepal.
- You may take the help of other persons who are skilled in both Nepali and English for translation and back-translation. You can even translate the test to your native tongue if you have one and if you want to research the people who speak your native tongue.”

Willing but Unable? The Time will Teach!

Some students are willing to learn skills and put in a lot of hard work. Still, they seem to be unable to learn. Definitely, there may be some weaknesses in the mentoring relationship, but we should wait till some time elapses before we know if they will persevere or quit. Despite the availability of many resources for free (like on YouTube) and from the home itself, it is strange, why students cannot learn the skills enough. Again, the lack of technological know-how may be to blame. There are other issues like shortage of time because of employment and family issues. In my opinion, their perseverance is the litmus test. Still, the mentors may teach skills for time management, and work-life balance. They can support by being proactive in the relationship.

Statistics: A Puzzle?

I remember that a student had dropped out of his master’s degree when he had failed to compute results from his quantitative data. He had a law degree as his backup; he might have dropped

out because he pursued a psychology degree as a pastime. Many students face the barrier of statistics. The larger problem is the statistics anxiety. As many as eight in 10 graduate students have statistics anxiety (Onwuegbuzie, 2004) and it may be the cause of delayed academic performance. In today's time when computer applications handle every computation, statistics should not be a barrier. Proteges should know when to use a statistic and how to interpret it. The calculation will be handled by the software, but the user should know how to do the steps in it to get the results. Currently, some students are found to outsource their data analysis to the outsiders at a very expensive rate. When the college knows well about the students' problems with statistics, it should make a mechanism to address their problems. There can be a data analysis assistance cell or paid consultation facilities at a reasonable price.

Planning Family and Something Else

Many students leave their thesis undone and bear a child. They get busy in rearing their newborns and procrastinate their research. Most of the female students have done this whereas some male students have attributed their delay to such a decision. They should know about family planning well. Family planning is about knowing when to bear children so that life becomes easy in career, finance, and everything else. Similar is the case with their employment. The students should know that they can get better opportunities if they enter into the workforce with a completed degree. Moreover, they can choose to be part-time employees until they are done with their thesis work.

Employment-Study Balance

As mentioned earlier, students can manage ways to strike a balance between jobs and study in different ways. Still, if they are disciplined enough and strive to complete research work during the six months of the last semester, they will have less to suffer. The management should establish good policies to enable students to complete their thesis by the end of the fourth semester. When I socialize the proteges, I encourage them to start early and put in hard work.

- “Doing research and writing a thesis takes a lot of time, maybe months. Please plan wisely and work hard to complete both on time.
- You need to do a lot of hard work for the thesis. Study the research articles and relevant other literature carefully for it.
- You need to know the research gap well. So, an intense study is the only option to find it.
- You may need to find relevant theory or make the “theoretical framework” based on available literature. So, study intensely.
- You should study the tool(s) you choose in detail.
- I cannot teach you data analysis from scratch. I am here for minor guidance. I assume that you know it already (from the learnings of earlier semesters).”

Things I Can Improve

I was more reactive to students. I majorly replied to the queries of the students via email or phone. However, I rarely proactively poked them to do the needed or showed the path to take at a particular point. Maybe I can get proactive and remind students. I can inquire them the progress of their work. This is what I learned from my Australian mentor. I can also be proactive to suggest things or send relevant resources to my students. Proteges can be stuck in the quagmire of confusion and indecision.

In some instances, I have been lenient because of my emotional attachment with proteges. These were because the students came in at the last minute to submit or they had invested a lot of time. There is no harm in becoming professionally demanding. So, I can be clearer during socialization that they have to plan ahead and work hard to accomplish their research. I have started some steps such as the following:

- “Doing research and writing a thesis takes a lot of time, maybe months. Please plan wisely and work hard to complete both on time. Hastily submitted report may not be accepted. Please do not wait for the eleventh hour.
- Good luck with your thesis!”

Discussion

Mentoring is not just an intermittent activity. In developed nations, mentoring is starting to get formal, structured, and purposeful (C. A. Mullen, 2008, p. xi), and is an organizational culture in academia. The college and university management should take initiative for planning, implementing, and evaluating the mentoring programs as a formal scheme. Mentoring should be taken as part of andragogy because it helps in career advancement and psychosocial support (Carol A. Mullen et al., 2008).

A mentoring relationship is equality-based, relational, and developmental (Carol A. Mullen & Klimaitis, 2021). Group mentoring has been suggested by the experts. This model can be adopted in our university also. Rather than a faculty supervising a student, a group of mentors can do the supervision. The teacher-student hierarchy can be made collegial. The new researchers need to be socialized by the mentors. The mentors need to be empathetic but should not stop being professionally demanding. They can be kind and proactively remind protege’s ideas to proceed further or poke them to remain motivated.

There can be nuances in what is important in the relationship. The mentors think that empathy, understanding, easy access, good communication, and enthusiasm are needed (Lee & Bush, 2003). Proteges think that enthusiasm and good communication are the most needed attributes in mentors. However, communication and negotiation can resolve the differences. The mentors can delegate authority to mentees to decide for themselves. However, interaction should be more intense

between mentor and mentee. Nepali students may not have been ready yet for the online feedback. The mentees should get enough guidance regarding the resources they need to rely on. Supervision may begin from the phase of proposal-making.

There is a need for big preparation to plan, implement and evaluate the mentoring effectiveness. For example, which student should be given which professor as supervisor should be based on some criteria rather than randomness. The university or college management can facilitate formalization and recognition of the mentoring relationship. It should use the thesis presentations as networking opportunities for researchers and marketing opportunities for colleges or universities. External examination of the thesis should be connected to the growth of university teachers; incumbent rather than retired professors should be the examiners. Funders like governments and organizations should be linked with students by university management.

The mentees should be passionate and dedicated. They should develop English and technological skills. They should be willing to do the needed to excel in their research skills. They should carefully strike the balance between family, education, and job. To accomplish the research skills, they may have to hone some management skills.

In the future, the unique cultural factors affecting the mentoring relationship can be studied. Such studies should build on the finding of studies in developed nations. Similarly, the insights from guruparampara (teacher-pupil lineage; Adluri, 2014) that existed in Eastern cultures can be consulted for theoretical frameworks or insights.

Conclusion

Mentoring can be used as a teaching method in MA, especially to train new researcher. The mentors should first provide orientation regarding the college or university culture, scope and methods of research, and the management skills. The mentees themselves should be disciplined and use mentoring relationship as a big learning opportunity. They should constantly work hard to hone their technical and human skills. The college or university should ease the teaching and learning activities. The mentoring to new researcher can help enhance the graduating student's career and improve psychosocial wellbeing. My experiences shared in this article may provide insights to increase effectiveness of mentoring to an early career researcher.

References

- Adams, T. E., Jones, S. H., & Ellis, C. (2015). *Autoethnography*. Oxford University Press.
- Adhikari, P. (2020). Psychological effects of the covid-19-induced lockdown 2020 among educated adults of Nepal. *New Trends in Psychology*, 2(2), 129–145.
- Adhikari, P. (2022a). A teacher's autoethnography on the effectiveness of semester system on a master's degree. *TU Annual publication*, 184–202. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7812385>

- Adhikari, P. (2022b). Future course of Nepalese psychology: A vision. In Y. Adhikari, S. Shrestha, & K. Sigdel (Eds.), *Nepalese Psychology: V.1* (pp. 133–144). Evincepub. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7820054>
- Adhikari, P., & McLaren, S. (2023). Functional impairment and depressive symptoms among older adults of rural nepal: The moderating role of three sources of social support. *Clinical Gerontologist*, 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.1080/07317115.2023.2187732>
- Adhuri, S. (2014). Śabdapramāṇa as a theological category in Vedānta Deśika's Tattvamuktākālāpa. *The Journal of Hindu Studies*, 7(1), 54–69.
- Awaya, A., McEwan, H., Heyler, D., Linsky, S., Lum, D., & Wakukawa, P. (2003). Mentoring as a journey. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 19(1), 45–56. [https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/S0742-051X\(02\)00093-8](https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/S0742-051X(02)00093-8)
- Burley, S., & Pomphrey, C. (2011). *Mentoring and coaching in schools: professional learning through collaborative inquiry*. Routledge.
- Commission for Investigation of Abuse of Authority. (2022). Notice for students studying in MA, MPhil and PhD levels for scholarship to conduct research in areas of corruption control and good governance promotion. <https://ciaa.gov.np/singleNotice/152>
- Gruber, J., Borelli, J. L., Prinstein, M. J., Clark, L. A., Davila, J., Klein, D. N., Gee, D. G., Levenson, R. W., Mendle, J., Olatunji, B. O., Rose, G. L., Saxbe, D., & Weinstock, L. M. (2020). Best practices in research mentoring in clinical science. *Journal of Abnormal Psychology*. <https://doi.org/10.1037/abn0000478>
- Lechuga, V. M. (2011). Faculty-graduate student mentoring relationships: mentors' perceived roles and responsibilities. *Higher Education*, 62(6), 757–771. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10734-011-9416-0>
- Lee, L. M., & Bush, T. (2003). Student mentoring in higher education: Hong Kong Baptist University. *Mentoring & Tutoring: Partnership in Learning*, 11(3), 263–271. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1361126032000138319>
- Lunsford, L. G., Crisp, G., Dolan, E. L., & Wuetherick, B. (2017). Mentoring in higher education. In *The SAGE Handbook of Mentoring* (Vol. 20, pp. 316–334). Sage Thousand Oaks, CA.
- Mullen, C. A. (Ed.). (2008). *The handbook of formal mentoring in higher education: A case study approach*. Christopher-Gordon Publishers.
- Mullen, C. A., & Klimaitis, C. C. (2021). Defining mentoring: a literature review of issues, types, and applications. *Annals of the New York Academy of Sciences*, 1483(1), 19–35. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1111/nyas.14176>

- Mullen, Carol A., Feyten, C. M., Holcomb, C., Kealy, W. A., & Keller, H. R. (2008). Launching a New Faculty Mentoring Program in a University Research Culture. In C. A. Mullen (Ed.), *The Handbook of Formal Mentoring in Higher Education: A Case Study Approach*, (pp. 25–53). Christopher-Gordon Publishers.
- Neophytou, E., Manwell, L. A., & Eikelboom, R. (2019). Effects of excessive screen time on neurodevelopment, learning, memory, mental health, and neurodegeneration: A scoping review. *International Journal of Mental Health and Addiction*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11469-019-00182-2>
- Onwuegbuzie, A. J. (2004). Academic procrastination and statistics anxiety. *Assessment & Evaluation in Higher Education*, 29(1), 3–19. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0260293042000160384>
- Pan, W., & Tang, M. (2005). Students' perceptions on factors of statistics anxiety and instructional strategies. *Journal of Instructional Psychology*, 32(3), 205.
- Robbins, S. P., & Judge, T. A. (2022). *Organizational behavior* (18th ed.). Pearson Education.
- Searby, L., Ballenger, J., & Tripses, J. (2015). Climbing the ladder, holding the ladder: The mentoring experiences of higher education female leaders. *Advancing Women in Leadership*, 35(98–107).
- Thomas, N., Bystydzienski, J., & Desai, A. (2015). Changing institutional culture through peer mentoring of women STEM faculty. *Innov High Educ*, 40(143–57). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10755-014-9300-9>
- Twenge, J. M., & Farley, E. (2021). Not all screen time is created equal: Associations with mental health vary by activity and gender. *Social Psychiatry and Psychiatric Epidemiology*, 56(2), 207–217. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00127-020-01906-9>
- University Grants Commission. (2021). *Research development and innovation programs implementation guidelines* (6th ed.).

विषयसूची

लेखकको नाम	विषय	पृष्ठ
चेतराज भट्ट	त्रिविमा क्षमता अभिवृद्धि केन्द्रको आवश्यकता	१
भूपप्रसाद धमला	त्रिविमा शिक्षण सिकाइको वर्तमान अवस्था र सुधारको सम्भावना	७
राजेन्द्र खनाल	न्यायालयका दृष्टिमा त्रिभुवन विश्वविद्यालय	१५
रामप्रसाद सुवेदी	वर्तमान समयमा सूचना र सञ्चारको अवस्था र कक्षाकोठामा यसको प्रयोग	२४
रूपा श्रेष्ठ	प्रविधिमैत्री आर्थिक व्यवस्थापन र आर्थिक अनुशासन	३२
विनोद जोशी	त्रिविमा विद्यमान करार शिक्षकहरूको समस्याको प्रकृति, निरूपण र कानुनी पक्षको विवेचना	४७
विनिल अर्याल	त्रिभुवन विश्वविद्यालयको विगत २५ वर्षमा भएका अनुसन्धान तथा प्रकाशनहरूको अध्ययन र विश्लेषण	५८
Manoj Karna	A Media Trial on Tribhuvan University's Examination Process in Recent Years	६८
Pralhad Adhikari	Mentoring a New Researcher: A Teacher's Learning	७७
Sunil Rawal	The Impact of Information Technology in Higher Education: A Sociological Analysis	९२
Sushmita Acharya	Status of Employees' Enablement: A case of Tribhuvan University	१०३

त्रिभुवन विश्वविद्यालय

त्रिवि वार्षिक दिवस प्रकाशन

TU Annual Publication

- प्रकाशक : त्रिवि, सूचना तथा जनसम्पर्क महाशाखा, कीर्तिपुर
 फोन नं. : ०१-४३३०३४६
 फ्याक्स : ९७७-१-४३३९९६४
 Email : info@tu.edu.np
 Website : www.tu.edu.np
 कम्प्यूटर डिजाइन : सरोज महर्जन
 मुद्रक : त्रिवि, छापाखाना, कीर्तिपुर, फोन नं. ४३३९३२०
 आवरण पृष्ठ : त्रिभुवन विश्वविद्यालय केन्द्रीय प्रविधि क्याम्पस, धरान

Follow us !

त्रिभुवन विश्वविद्यालय वार्षिक

दिवस प्रकाशन - २०८०

प्रकाशन समिति

प्रा.डा. शिवलाल भुसाल शिक्षाध्यक्ष, त्रिभुवन विश्वविद्यालय	संयोजक
प्रा.डा. ध्रुवकुमार गौतम कार्यकारी निर्देशक, योजना निर्देशनालय	सदस्य
प्रा.डा. जीवलाल सापकोटा विभागीय प्रमुख, अङ्ग्रेजी केन्द्रीय विभाग	सदस्य
प्रा.डा. बलराम प्रसाई विभागीय प्रमुख, भाषाविज्ञान केन्द्रीय विभाग	सदस्य
प्रा.डा. खगेन्द्रप्रसाद लुइटेल् विभागीय प्रमुख, नेपाली केन्द्रीय विभाग	सदस्य
योगेन्द्रप्रसाद दाहाल प्रमुख, सूचना तथा जनसम्पर्क महाशाखा	सदस्यसचिव

२०८० असार १२ गते मङ्गलबार

२७ जुन २०२३